

On the Catalytic Combustion Behaviors of CH₄ in a MCFC Power Generation System

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Abstract—Catalytic combustion is generally accepted as an environmentally preferred alternative for the generation of heat and power from fossil fuels mainly due to its advantages related to the stable combustion under very lean conditions with low emissions of NO_x, CO, and UHC at temperatures lower than those occurred in conventional flame combustion. Despite these advantages, the commercial application of catalytic combustion has been delayed because of complicated reaction processes and the difficulty in developing appropriate catalysts with the required stability and durability. To develop the catalytic combustors, detailed studies on the combustion characteristics of catalytic combustion should be conducted. To the end, in current research, quantitative studies on the combustion characteristics of the catalytic combustors, with a Pd-based catalyst for MCFC power generation systems, relying on numerical simulations have been conducted. In addition, data from experimental studies of variations in outlet temperatures and fuel conversion, taken after operating conditions have been used to validate the present numerical approach. After introducing the governing equations for mass, momentum, and energy equations as well as a description of catalytic combustion kinetics, the effects of the excess air ratio, space velocity, and inlet gas temperature on the catalytic combustion characteristics are extensively investigated. Quantitative comparisons are also conducted with previous experimental data. Finally, some concluding remarks are presented.

Keywords—Catalytic combustion, Methane, BOP, MCFC power generation system, Inlet temperature, Excess air ratio, Space velocity.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE optimum energy carrier for MCFC systems being developed for commercial applications is hydrogen. Of all the potential sources of hydrogen, the most attractive source is natural gas, because it is widely available, clean, and can be converted to hydrogen relatively easily [1]. When natural gas is used as a fuel for MCFC systems, the general composition of off-gas from the anode is 36% CO₂, 45% H₂O, 15% H₂, 2% CO, and 2% CH₄ by volume. A combustor is needed to burn out these gases in order to prevent emissions and increase the overall efficiency of the fuel cell systems [2], [3].

In most cases, however, perfect combustion is quite difficult to achieve with a conventional combustor because the anode off-gas includes high concentrations of inert gases, such as H₂O and CO₂. Therefore, a catalytic combustor, which generally operates at relatively low temperature and has good combustion efficiency even in limited conditions with high concentrations of H₂O and CO₂, in comparison with those of conventional combustor, resulting in a reduction of thermal NO_x, CO, and

UHC emissions [4], [5], is introduced to MCFC systems. Catalytic combustion has generally been accepted as an environmentally preferred alternative for heat and power generation systems, allowing fossil fuels to be burned efficiently, in fuel concentrations outside flammability limits, at temperatures lower than those used in flame combustion, and with fewer undesirable combustion by-products [6]-[8].

Meanwhile, catalytic combustion involves complicated reaction processes that are controlled by heterogeneous chemistry (for examples, the diffusion of reactants to the catalytic surface, adsorption, surface reaction, desorption, diffusion of products from the surface) and transport phenomena of mass, momentum, and energy, in addition to homogeneous chemistry [9]. Consequently, the analysis and optimization of operating conditions for the stable operation of methane-based catalytic combustion are necessary to apply such a system to natural gas-based MCFC power generation systems. To ensure stable operation in such systems, the combustion of CH₄ is most important among off-gas components, because the reaction of CH₄ starts at a relatively higher temperature than that of H₂ and CO [10], [12]. In this study, therefore, CH₄ catalytic combustion characteristics are the main focus. Here, the Pd-based catalyst commonly used for catalytic combustion of CH₄ is adopted.

Several recent efforts have begun to address the catalytic combustion characteristics of CH₄ with a Pd-based catalyst for real applications. Dalla Betta et al. [13] showed that preheating is required for the ignition of CH₄ by illustrating the ignition/extinction catalyst performance. Kuper et al. [14] and Griffin et al. [15] showed that the PdO/Pd transition temperature range within which the activity of a catalyst is reduced is between 750 and 850°C. Hong [3] and Lee et al. [16] conducted an experimental study to investigate the importance of various parameters such as inlet temperature, space velocity, gas composition, and the excess air ratio for complete combustion. Recently, Deshmukh and Vlachos [17] proposed a reduced mechanism for methane and one-step rate expressions for fuel-lean catalytic combustion of small alkanes on noble metals.

In this paper, therefore, numerical investigations on the CH₄ catalytic combustion characteristics according to various parameters are conducted to examine the optimal operating conditions. Firstly, after introducing the governing equations adopted in this work, the numerical approach, which entails a comparison with experimental data given by Hong [3], is validated. Next, catalyst performance studies with different excess air ratio and space velocity are reviewed, and the optimal design characteristics are determined from them. The

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design points of combustor systems are fixed and used to scale up the catalytic combustor and the following parametric studies according to variations in operating conditions for the performance evaluation of catalytic combustors. The effects of various operating conditions such as inlet temperature and H₂ addition on reaction behavior in the adopted catalytic combustor under actual conditions in the 250kW MCFC system are then investigated. Finally, some concluding remarks are presented.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

A. Governing Equations

The catalytic combustor considered in this work is a part of the balance of plant (BOP) of the MCFC power generation systems depicted in Fig. 1. Since the catalytic reactions occur on the catalyst surface, the reactants have to be transported to the external gas-solid interface. Modeling the overall combustion process, therefore, requires consideration of both the physical transport and the chemical kinetic steps [18]-[20]. In general, there is a boundary layer between the bulk fluid stream and the solid surface, within which velocity, concentration, and temperature vary. Species transport, from the bulk fluid stream to the solid catalytic surface, can have a limiting effect on the rate of the catalytic reaction. In this work, the reactions are considered a one-step global reaction in terms of fuel composition [21], [22]. Therefore, the influence of adsorption and desorption of species on the catalytic surface must be considered in formulating the reaction rates. Here, the commonly used Langmuir-Hinshelwood-Hougen-Watson type rate equations [15] are used to model the catalytic reactions.

Under the assumption that the radial transport effects of a honeycomb-type catalytic converter are smaller than those of axial heat transfer, the entire converter can be represented by a single channel [18], [23], [24]. While the effects taking place are convective, diffusive and conductive transport occur in the gas phase, and mass and energy can transfer through the boundary layer, diffusion and catalytic conversion in the washcoat and conduction in the solid phase also can occur. In addition, neglecting the radial gradients in the channel, a transient and one-dimensional (in the axial direction) conservation equation suffices to describe thermodynamic and fluid dynamic characteristics. Under these assumptions, the differential conservation equations for the mass, momentum, and energy of a single channel can be written as follows [25].

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the MCFC power generation system

TABLE I
BASIC GAS COMPOSITION OF THE CATALYTIC COMBUSTOR BASED ON OFF-GASES FROM THE ANODE

Species	Mass flow rate (kg/hr)		Mole fraction
	5 kW	250 kW	
H ₂	0.15	7.67	0.045
CO	0.33	16.75	0.007
CO ₂	7.89	394.36	0.105
CH ₄	0.15	7.41	0.005
H ₂ O	4.12	206.13	0.135
Air ($\lambda=4$)	34.55	1,727.73	0.702
Total	47.2	2,360.04	1.000

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The one-step global reactions for H₂, CO, and CH₄ are used to conduct a characteristic analysis of the catalytic combustion, i.e.,

The reaction rate expressions are, of the Langmuir-Hinshelwood type which is most commonly used for analyzing catalytic combustion with inhibition terms [15], [16] such as

$$\dot{r}_1 = K_1 y_{\text{H}_2} y_{\text{O}_2} / D, \quad \dot{r}_2 = K_2 y_{\text{CO}} y_{\text{O}_2} / D, \quad \dot{r}_3 = K_3 y_{\text{CH}_4} y_{\text{O}_2} / D \quad (4)$$

$$D = T_s \left(1 + K_2 y_{\text{CO}} + K_3 y_{\text{CH}_4} \right)^2 \left(1 + K_4 y_{\text{CO}}^2 y_{\text{CH}_4}^2 \right) \left(1 + K_5 y_{\text{NO}}^{0.7} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$K_i = k_i \exp(-T_{A,i} / T_s) \quad (6)$$

where k_i and $T_{A,i}$ are the frequency factor and the activation energy, respectively and y_k is the mole fraction of species k . The kinetic parameters are calculated by comparing the light-off characteristics of the catalytic reaction with the optimization process by using iSIGHTTM [26]. The kinetic

parameters of catalytic combustion of methane are as follows :
 $k_1 = 1.1 \times 10^6 \text{ kmol}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$, $k_2 = 65.5$, $k_3 = 2.08 \times 10^3$, $k_4 = 3.98$, $k_5 = 4.79 \times 10^5$, $T_{A,1} = 6.45 \times 10^3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{A,2} = -9.61 \times 10^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{A,3} = -3.61 \times 10^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{A,4} = -1.1611 \times 10^4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $T_{A,5} = 3.733 \times 10^3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

B. Numerical Analysis

In this study, methane originating from natural gas is used as the main fuel of the catalytic combustor. The conditions simulated correspond to the experimental study done by Hong [3]. Table I shows the basic gas composition used as the inlet condition, based on the off-gas composition from the anode, under a fuel utilization rate of 60% of the MCFC stack. A Pd/Ce/Ni- Al_2O_3 catalyst, which contains not only Pd(2 wt.%), but also Ce and Ni, is used because the concentration of H_2O obstructing catalyst activity is high [27]. The physical properties of the catalysts used in this study are as follows: monolith volume of 0.00141 m^3 , length of monolith of 0.1m, cell density of 300cps, wall thickness of 8 mil, washcoat thickness of 5 mil, number of grid points of 20, density of $2500 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$, thermal conductivity of $3 \text{ W}/\text{mK}$, and specific heat of $800 \text{ J}/\text{kgK}$.

The governing equations are analyzed with BOOSTTM of AVL [15] by adopting the thermo chemical properties of the fuel and catalysts used in this study. Here, the number of grid points is 20 and the adiabatic condition is used at the wall, while the outlet condition of the catalytic combustor is assigned an atmospheric pressure of 0.1MPa.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Model Validation

First, a comparison between the numerical and experimental results of the CH_4 mole fraction and the outlet temperature is conducted using the basic gas composition indicated in Section II B and the operating conditions such that the inlet temperature is 290°C , the space velocity is $24,000 \text{ hr}^{-1}$, and the excess air ratio is 4 under the conditions of a 5kW MCFC system. In order to completely combust CH_4 , supplemental fuels such as CO and H_2 are added in ordered intervals as shown in Fig. 2. Here, it can be found that CH_4 , which is initially supplied at $t=110\text{s}$, remains unconverted over the catalyst before any supplemental fuel is supplied. After CO is supplied, however, CH_4 starts to react, the temperature increases by 50°C , a small amount. Dramatic variations of the CH_4 mole fraction and temperature are observed when H_2 is used as an additional fuel. In Fig. 2, it is found that the CH_4 mole fraction and temperature increase steeply when 40% H_2 is supplied. In addition, when 70% H_2 is supplied, almost all of the CH_4 is converted into the products, and the temperature reaches almost 580°C . The final temperature increase to 640°C is due mainly to the H_2 reaction, which is supplied at $t=1,700\text{s}$. Note that the simulation data using the kinetic parameters indicated in Section II A agrees well with the experimental data [3].

Fig. 2 Comparison of simulation and experiment results of the CH_4 mole fraction and outlet temperature for the case of $T_{in}=285^\circ\text{C}$, $\lambda=4$ and $\text{SV}=24,000 \text{ hr}^{-1}$

Fig. 3 Effects of the excess air ratio on the CH_4 conversion rate and the outlet temperature when $\text{SV}=24,000 \text{ hr}^{-1}$

B. Effect of the Excess Air Ratio

The excess air ratio is the volumetric ratio of air to fuel present combustion. It is known that a low excess air ratio can lead to deactivation of the catalyst because of high combustion temperatures. In contrast, a high excess air ratio creates unburned fuel, which is supplied to the cathode and may cause unexpected problems in the MCFC stack. Consequently, the decision of the proper excess air ratio is quite important for the stable operation of a catalytic combustor.

Fig. 3 shows the effect of the excess air ratio on the CH_4 conversion and the outlet temperature with three different inlet temperatures of 400, 290, and 165°C with the basic gas composition. Here, the space velocity is $24,000 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ at $\lambda=4$, but steadily increases because of the increase in volumetric flow resulting from the air supply addition, even though the reactor volume is the same. When the inlet temperatures are 400°C and 290°C , all of the CH_4 is converted into products, regardless of the excess air ratio, because the inlet temperature is high enough for the fuel to react completely. In particular, when the inlet temperature is 400°C , it is very important that the outlet temperature exceeds 800°C , at which point the deactivation of the Pd catalyst may occur if the excess air ratio is less than three. Meanwhile, when the inlet temperature is as low as 165°C and the excess air ratio exceeds five, the CH_4 conversion

rate decreases sharply. For this reason, the excess air ratio has to be maintained between three and five for stable operation of the catalytic combustor considered in this study.

Fig. 4 Effects of the space velocity on the CH₄ conversion rate and the outlet temperature when $T_{in}=165^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\lambda=4$

Fig. 5 Effects of inlet temperature on the CH₄ conversion rate and the outlet temperature when $\lambda=4$ and $SV= 20,000\text{hr}^{-1}$

C. Effect of Space Velocity

The space velocity (SV), representing the ratio of the volumetric flow rate and the reactor volume, is related to the residence time of fueling gases in a channel. Determining SV is very important because a low SV can make fuel and air mixtures react even under stringent conditions, such as with a low inlet temperature or a high excess air ratio. In this section, therefore, the effect of SV on CH₄ conversion and outlet temperature is investigated for a low inlet temperature of 165°C.

Fig. 4 shows the effects of the SV on CH₄ conversion and the catalyst outlet temperature at an inlet temperature of 165°C with the basic gas composition. As expected, both CH₄ conversion and outlet temperature decrease as the SV increases, because the residence time of the fuel decreases in the catalytic region. In addition, the most rapid decrease of the conversion rate is seen when the SV is between 20,000 and 30,000 hr⁻¹. For the stable operation of the catalytic combustor, the SV must be below 20,000 hr⁻¹, at which level most of the fuel can react, although the inlet temperature is 165°C. Thus, in this study, the proper excess air ratio and space velocity are 4 and 20,000 hr⁻¹,

respectively. In addition, the design points are used to scale up the catalytic combustor by conducting parametric studies under the expected actual operating conditions of 250kW MCFC power generation systems.

D. Effect of Inlet Gas Temperature

Parametric studies, using various operating conditions such as inlet temperature and the H₂ supply rate under the 250kW MCFC system, are conducted preliminarily to assess the performance of the catalytic combustor under the actual conditions of MCFC power generation systems. In advance, the effect of inlet gas temperature on catalytic combustion characteristics is investigated because the inlet gas temperature is an important parameter for initiating and maintaining the reaction over the catalyst and should be raised to exceed the light-off temperature (LOT), so that the fuel component sufficiently reacts on the catalyst surface [28], [29]. Although some studies about inlet temperature are discussed in Section III B, a more extensive investigation of inlet temperature effects is conducted in this section.

In Fig. 5, both the CH₄ conversion rate and outlet temperature variations are illustrated with various inlet temperatures. Only CH₄, except for H₂ and CO, among the fuel components of basic gas composition is supplied when $\lambda=4$. As expected, the higher inlet gas temperature causes more fuel conversion and higher outlet temperatures. In particular, it can be seen that a value of T_{50} (i.e., 50% fuel conversion) is found between 380°C and 400°C. In addition, for inlet temperatures above 420°C, the CH₄ conversion rate reaches almost 100%, and the outlet temperature is approximately 550°C. This suggests that an inlet temperature of 380°C is needed for complete combustion of CH₄ in this type of BOP for MCFC power generation applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work numerical investigations are performed to examine the catalytic combustion characteristics under various conditions by altering parameters, such as the excess air ratio, space velocity, and inlet temperature. From this parametric study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) The outlet temperature and conversion rate of the fuel component decrease with increases in the excess air ratio. An excess air ratio between 3 and 5 is best for ensuring the stable operation of the catalytic combustor.
- (2) When the inlet temperature is 165°C, CH₄ conversion and outlet temperature decrease as the SV increases because the residence time of the fuel decreases in the catalytic region. In addition, the most rapid decrease of the conversion rate is observed when the SV is between 20,000 and 30,000 hr⁻¹. For complete combustion of CH₄, the space velocity should be below 20,000 hr⁻¹.
- (3) The fuel conversion and outlet temperature increase as the inlet temperature increases. When the inlet temperature rises to 400°C, the most rapid increase of the CH₄ conversion rate is achieved.

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